

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING LISTENING

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Annotation: The problem of effective organization of teaching listening for professional purposes of university students is considered; an overview of modern requirements and existing approaches to this methodological problem is shown; a description of the author's approach is given; examples are given from their own experience in organizing the process of learning to listen to professional texts. Professionally oriented listening is analyzed as a goal and a means of teaching at a university, which from a functional and pragmatic point of view implies mastery of different types of listening in accordance with the content of audio materials.

Keywords: English for Special Purposes; audio materials; listening; types of listening; listening training.

INTRODUCTION

Listening to foreign speech is one of the most difficult types of speech activity to master, since listening is an active speech-thinking process, during which all mental and mental mechanisms are working hard to perceive sounding speech, perception received in sound form. information, its recognition, interpretation and understanding of meaning [1]. In the conditions of the university, the problem of teaching foreign language, in particular, English, texts of professionally oriented content to listen to is particularly acute.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Despite the fact that interesting works on this topic have recently appeared [3, 4], the effective organization of listening training for professional purposes has not lost its significance and relevance. This article describes the author's approach and experience in teaching students to listen to professional English-language texts.

The essence of professionally oriented listening training lies in the formation of the skills of perception and understanding of the interlocutor's statement in a foreign language, generated in a monologue form or in the process of dialogue in accordance with a certain real professional field and work situation. At the same time, listening itself can act both as a learning goal (perception and interpretation of English speech by ear, followed by analysis of the information received and its use), and as a means of learning / self-learning (audio and video materials are used by students as a source information in the preparation of creative tasks), and as a means of control/self-control of knowledge of the studied lexical and grammatical material at the final stage of working with it.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The content of audio texts must meet the following criteria: authenticity of sources; professional orientation of information: reflection of areas of activity, situations of professional communication, professionally significant topics; functional, stylistic and genre correlation with the acquired specialty; representation of samples of monologue and dialogic speech; the availability of information on sociocultural and regional studies; taking into account the level of professional and language training of students: the corresponding level of difficulty of the lexical and grammatical content of the text; a certain pace of sound, the distinctness of the announcer's pronunciation; inclusion of a noise-carrying background in the audio recording; phonetic coloring (see details about the features of audio texts in [2]).

Within the framework of professionally oriented education, the choice of audio texts should correspond to the genre and functional-stylistic features characteristic of professional areas of communication. Based on this criterion, audio texts should reflect such genres of scientific style as a report, lecture, scientific

conversation, discussion, presentation of projects and production style of speech - instruction, message, description of the production process / technical device / technology. According to the forms of oral speech, audio materials are monologue and dialogic statements. Monologue (lectures, audio recordings of scientific, popular science works, information radio broadcasts, documentaries and TV programs, audio and video materials that are freely available on the Internet, including on various professional websites or YouTube [1]) are the most more popular form of audio texts in academic and professional terms. Successful listening of monologue statements depends on background conceptual knowledge of the subject matter; from the ability to differentiate between essential and non-essential; on the ability of listeners (students) to focus attention for a long time, to know the lexical-grammatical and stylistic features of oral lectures (ellipses, hesitations, repetitions, contractions, academic professionalism, jargon, etc.); understand large and complex segments of spoken speech. Learning to listen to dialogic speech takes place in two directions: a student can either be an active participant in this conversation, while listening acts as a component of oral speech communication during classroom classes, or indirectly, during a telephone conversation or a conversation with using modern communication tools, such as Skype, whose participants alternately act as a speaker, then as a listener, or as a passive listener, without being able to influence the course of the conversation, ask again or clarify some details (listening to the dialogue).

When developing a strategy for teaching listening to the above audio texts, it is also necessary to take into account the type of listening and the mental processes of perception/interpretation of information involved in its implementation. It should be noted that any work on audio texts includes three stages:

- 1) motivational and incentive (attitude, motive and goal);
- 2) analytical-synthetic (perception and processing of the text);
- 3) executive (understanding) [2].

Each stage has its own set of tasks: 1) pre-audit; 2) during the audition; 3) following the audition.

During the motivational-incentive stage, orientation takes place, students are tuned in to the type of text that they will hear, and the information that they will need to extract from what they have listened to. At this stage, students are instructed which text they will listen to (interview with ...; lecture on ...; dialogue in ...); provide the necessary background information about the text; let you listen to an abbreviated, simplified or slowed down version of the recording before listening to the full text; highlight and read together with the teacher key words and expressions that occur in the text; offer photographs, diagrams, drawings for study; provide an opportunity to read the summary. For example, “Listen to this lecture about FOR (flight data recorder). Underline the correct alternatives in the specification chart”, “Listen to a demonstration of a life raft and underline the correct details”, “Listen to this talk about vacuum formation. Tick the objects that are used in the process: air pump, hopper, powder, cylinder, mold with holes, solid mold, heater, pellets, thermoplastic sheet” [4].

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we note that training in professionally oriented listening in universities plays an important role in the preparation of highly professional specialists who are able to take an active part in various situations of international cooperation. The ability to listen and understand professional English speech is a key moment in the communication of professionals. This must and can be learned within the framework of a university program under the guidance of a teacher and in the process of independent work.

REFERENCES

1. Galskova, N. D. Theory of teaching foreign languages. Linguodidactics and methodology / N. D. Galskova, N. I. Gez. - M. : Academy, 2016. - 336 p.

2. Federal State Educational Standards for Higher Education (FSES HE; FSES 3+). (date of access: 28.04.2015).
3. Oliya, X. (2022). Educational Innovation as a Factor of Modernization of Teaching System. *Eurasian Journal of Learning and Academic Teaching*, 6, 52-54.
4. Гаппарова, Т. Г., & Хайдарова, О. К. (2020). ПУТИ И СРЕДСТВА ВОСПИТАНИЯ У СТУДЕНТОВ ТВОРЧЕСКОГО ОТНОШЕНИЯ К ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОМУ ТРУДУ. *Наука и мир*, 2(3), 40-41.
5. Хайдарова, О. К. (2021). НАУКА И МИР. *НАУКА И МИР Учредители: Издательство Научное обозрение*, 2(4), 52-54.
6. Хайдарова, О. К., & Бокиев, Б. У. (2016). Педагогический опыт преподавателя на современном этапе. *Молодой ученый*, (11), 1572-1574.
7. Гаппарова, Т. Г., & Хайдарова, О. К. (2013). ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОБЩЕНИЕ КАК ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЕ ЗВЕНО В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ УЧИТЕЛЯ. *SCIENCE AND WORLD*, 47.
8. Akbarova, L. U. (2023). MAMLAKATLARNING IQTISODIY INTEGRATSIYA JARAYONLARIDAGI ISHTIROKINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA RAQAMLI MARKETING TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH USULLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(1-2), 84-91.
9. Jabbarov, N. (2010). What is education. *Tashkent. Ma'naviyat*.
10. Jabborov, N. (2010). What is enlightenment.
11. Erkin, E., Dilmurod, M., & Navbakhor, K. (2022). MEDICINAL SCHIZOPHYLLUM COMMUNA FR. THE FIRST REPORT OF THE FUNGUS WHICH IS DISTRIBUTED IN THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN. *Universum: химия и биология*, (11-3 (101)), 13-16.
12. Erkin, E., Jamila, S., & Dilmurod, M. (2022). SCHIZOPHYLLUM COMMUNASI FR. ON THE TERRITORY OF UZBEKISTAN ISOLATION OF PURE CULTURE OF MEDICINAL FUNGUS. *Universum: химия и биология*, (6-4 (96)), 4-7.

13. Sherkulova, J. P., Mustafaev, I. M., Sharopova, M. A., Chariev, R. R., & Eshonkulov, E. Y. (2020). Micromycetes Of Class Leotiomycetes Distributed On Ornamental Trees Introduced In The Conditions Of The Southern Part Of Uzbekistan. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 7(03), 2020.
14. Iroda, R. (2022). Application of the concept of " word" in oral speech. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(05), 171-173.
15. Odiljonovna, R. I. (2023). VAQT KONSEPTINING PRAGMALINGVISTIK TADQIQI.
16. Рахмонова, И. О. (2022). СЎЗ УМУМФИЛОЛОГИК ТУШУНЧА СИФАТИДА. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(11), 346-349.
17. Rahmanova, I., & Mamatkulova, X. (2022). INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDA VAQT KONSEPTINING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры*, 2(12), 47-50.
18. Тилавов, М. Т., & Хамроев, С. Б. (2022). ОСОБЕННОСТИ КОГНИТИВНЫХ НАРУШЕНИЙ ПРИ ШИЗОФРЕНИИ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ТАКТИКА ЛЕЧЕНИЯ. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(10), 459-464.